

Identifying Researcher Positionality and Bias

Transformative Research Unit for Equity
Equity-Centered Methodology Tools

Positionality Map Directions

First tier (rectangles in blue circles): Fill in the broad aspects of your social identity in the rectangles sitting in blue circles. There are two blank circles where you can add salient dimensions of your social identity to the blank circles.

Second tier (rectangles): Identify the privileges and disadvantages that society affords you due to aspects of your social identity. This may include values attached to these aspects or how you might interact with the world. For example, if in the first tier of sexuality I write “heterosexual,” under the second tier I may write, “accepted” or “privileged,” noting how my identity is valued in society and what benefits it affords.

After you have reflected on the dimensions of identity and how they might impact your life, review and answer a few questions from each topic area. When reflecting, select a specific project to use as reference.

After you have answered the selected questions, consider writing a few statements summarizing your positionality. See examples of positionality statements [here](#).

Understanding Your Identity

Review the different aspects of your identity. Which are most salient for how you experience the world currently? Why?

- Has that changed over time? Has your awareness of the impact of these characteristics changed over time?

Which aspects of your identity are most salient for how others see you? Why? How is that different, if at all, from what is most salient for you?

What is your racial and cultural background? How does that influence how you experience the world? What do you believe about race and culture in society?

How are your personal characteristics or aspects of identity sources of power and privilege? Or, alternatively, marginalization and disadvantage?

Thinking About Yourself in Relation to Participants

Select a specific project that you are working on when answering these questions.

What are similarities and differences between aspects of your identity and those of participants in the project or study? Thinking of these similarities or differences, what are the implications for how you engage in or conduct the work? How would aspects of your identity impact the way you interact with project or study participants?

How would participants in the project or study view you? How may that influence your interactions? What are the implications for how you engage or conduct the work?

What are some assumptions, perceptions, or biases you have about the communities or populations that are part of the project? What informed these perceptions? How might these assumptions, perceptions, or biases influence the project?

- What are some favorable or positive biases?
- What are some unfavorable or negative biases?

Thinking About Yourself in Relation to the Subject of Your Work

What are some assumptions, perceptions, biases you have about the intervention, program, or initiative that you are studying or working on? What informed these perceptions?

What are your assumptions, perceptions, or biases about the client funding the evaluation and/or organizations offering the programs and services? What informed these perceptions?

What experiences, including your racialized and cultural experiences, influenced these perspectives?

What are possible tensions between the client, the initiative, and your interests and beliefs? How will you negotiate these tensions?

What are some favorable or positive biases?

What are some unfavorable or negative biases?

Process of Engaging in Your Work

Which aspects of your identity, background, and/or past experiences influence what you often emphasize in your studies or projects? How you approach a study or project? In this specific study or project?

What frameworks or theories do you privilege in your study or project? Why those? Who developed them? What were they used for in the past? How do they relate to the context of this project? How, if at all, will they benefit this study or project? Harm this study or project?

Which aspects of your identity, background, and/or past experiences influence how you interpret your research or study findings?

Was there a time you privileged certain pieces of information or sources (e.g., role or person) more than others? What was the situation and what informed your decision?

Was there a time you privileged one data source or methodology over another? What was the situation and what informed your decision?

Which trends do you further investigate, and which trends do you not? What informs your decision?

What experiences, including your racialized and cultural experiences, influenced these decisions or approaches?

How might these assumptions, preferences, or biases influence this study or project? What do you want to be mindful of during the study or project process?

What does recognition of your power mean for this study or project? How can you refrain from reinforcing your social context in this study or project?

How will you attend to your own convictions and beliefs about race and culture in this study or project?

Sources:

Holmes, A. G. D. (2020). Researcher positionality—A consideration of its influence and place in qualitative research—A new researcher guide. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 8(4), 1–10.

Malterud, Kirsti. (2001). Qualitative research: Standards, challenges, and guidelines. *The Lancet*, 358(9280), 483–488.

Milner IV, H. R. (2007). Race, culture, and researcher positionality: Working through dangers seen, unseen, and unforeseen. *Educational researcher*, 36(7), 388–400.

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